

A Study to Evaluate the Effectiveness of Pranayama on Stress Management among Staff Nurses in Selected Settings at Jaipur

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Abstract: Introduction: Stress from many sources has been reported for some time by student nurses. The sources are like academic sources, parental expectations, and competition for grades, relationships and career choices.¹ Academic sources of stress like examinations, long hours of study, assignments and grades, lack of free time, and lack of timely feedback after their performance, special elements of the academic programme like arrangement and conduction of workshops, also produce stress among student nurses. And also clinical sources of stress like while taking care of critically ill patients, interpersonal conflict with peer group, insecurity about personal clinical competence, fear related to complete their clinical requirements, dealing with uncooperative patients, work overload, prolonged standing, learning psychomotor skills, e.g. administering injections and performing catheterization, have also been associated with high levels of stress.² In addition, stress leads to psychological morbidity which may have profound adverse consequences for individual nursing students.³ Nursing student's experiences of their clinical practice provide greater insight to develop an effective clinical teaching strategy in nursing education. They experienced stress as a result of feeling incompetent and lack of professional nursing skills and knowledge to take care of various patients in the clinical setting.⁴ There are numerous stressors for the students to develop stress in nursing education like, using critical thinking skills during their written examination.⁵ When compared with general student population the nursing students perceive more stress.⁶ **Design:** One group pretest posttest, pre experimental design was selected for the study. **Subjects:** The participants were 60 staff nurses from selected hospitals at Jaipur. **Methods:** Purposive sampling technique was used for the present study. **Data collection tool:** A stress rating scale was used to collect data from the themes. **Data analysis:** The obtained data was analysed by using descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequency, percentage, means, and variance was used to explain socio-demographic variables and to assess the extent the extent of stress. The extent of significance was set at 0.05 levels. **Results:** within the pre intervention stage, the subject had mild stress with a mean of fifty $.6 \pm 7.9$, whereas in post intervention, there was an enormous mean stress reduction/management of 31.0 ± 9.1 . An enormous association was found between age, gender, status, transportation facilities, awareness of pranayama and source of knowledge and mean pre intervention stress score. **Conclusion:** In pre intervention, 46.7% of the themes had moderate stress whereas in post intervention all the themes had only mild stress. The study findings indicate that the pranayama program was effective for stress reduction/management among staff nurses. **Keywords:** Pranayama, Stress, Staff nurses.

Introduction

Stress is the consequence of failure of an organism-human or animal to reply appropriately to emotional or physical threats, weather actual or imagined. It is a serious hazard of the fashionable world affecting all people no matter age, gender, education, occupation, domiciliary

status, finance, religion, race ethnicity and nationality¹. Stress can provide the stimulus for the change and growth and in some respect some stress is positive and even necessary. However an excessive amount of stress may end in poor judgment, physical illness and inability to cope².

Yoga offers many breathing skills for stress affected individuals. These yogic breathing techniques are termed as pranayama. Pranayama consists of various ways of inhaling, exhaling and retention of prana. Pranayama is the simplest practice to reduce stress³. Stress could also be a kind of hysteria and discomfort stemming usually from lack of rest or constant exposure to high complicated situations. Stress may result from many things, both physical and psychological pressures and deadlines at work, problems with loved ones, the need to pay bills, etc are just a couple of the apparent matters of stress for several people⁴. Everyone experiences some form of stress from time to time and normally the healthy person is able to adopt to long term stress or cope up with short term stress until it passes. Stress can place heavy demands on a person, however in all of the human dimensions and if the person is unable to adopt or cope up with the stress, illnesses can result⁵.

Need for the study

It is obvious that stress is present among nursing students. Excessive stress can be harmful to student's academic performance. Additionally, students who perceive their stress levels as very high often will become depressed.⁶ Researchers at the All India Institute of Medical Sciences in New Delhi have discovered a clear link between rhythmic breathing process and a state of relaxed alertness and recommended the practice of Pranayama for beating stress.^{7,8}

Objectives

1. Assess the extent of stress among staff nurses as perceived by them
2. Provide pranayama for workers nurses
3. Assess the extent of stress after providing pranayama among staff nurses
4. Determine the association between pre intervention perceived stress and selected socio demographic variable.

Assumptions

Staff nurses in their work have significant amount of stress because of self-direction and desire to make the only use of their capabilities to satisfy their own responsibilities.

- a) Stress should be avoided.
- b) Staff nurses can realize their stress level

Hypothesis

H1: The mean post intervention stress score of the staff nurses are significantly but their mean pre intervention stress scores.

H2: there's an enormous association between the pre intervention perceived stress and thus the chosen socio-demographic variables.

Research Methodology

Research Approach: Pre experimental approach

Research Design: One group pretest posttest design

Study variables: Stress among staff nurses

Extraneous Variable

This refers to the socio-demographic variables like age, gender, status, religion, kind of family, number of kids, family income, educational qualification, experience, hobbies, working shifts, transportation facilities, awareness of pranayama and source of knowledge. The study was conducted at two hospitals. The target population for the study was the staff nurses working in

these two hospitals. So on assess the effectiveness of pranayama on stress reduction among staff nurses, purposive sampling technique was used.

Sampling Criteria

Inclusive Criteria

- ✓ Working at selected settings at Jaipur
- ✓ Willing to practice Pranayama

Exclusion Criteria

- ✓ Diagnosed with medical conditions like DM, hypertension, and asthma
- ✓ Practicing pranayama daily

Development and outline of tools

Section A: Socio-demographic proforma

Section B: Perceived stress scale

Results

In the pre intervention stage, the themes had mild stress with a mean of fifty .6%±.7.9, where as in post intervention, there was an enormous mean stress reduction of 31.0±9.1. An enormous association was found between age, gender, status, transportation facilities, awareness of pranayama and source of knowledge and mean pre intervention stress score.

Conclusion

In the pre intervention stage, 46.7% of the themes had moderate stress, whereas within the post intervention all the themes had mild stress. The study findings indicate that the pranayama program was effective for stress reduction among staff nurses.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares there are no conflicts of interest.

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